

Guanylalkylureas and their Metallic Complexes. Part. VIII. Copper(II), Nickel(II), and Palladium (II) Complexes of Guanylalkoxyethylureas

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Dicyandiamide and alkoxyethanols (namely, methoxy-, ethoxy- and butoxyethanol) have been found to react in presence of copper acetate to form the rose-red coloured complex copper-bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea acetate. The reagents, guanylalkoxyethylurea sulphates, were obtained after decomposing the complex copper sulphates by H_2S . These respond to the usual tests of guanylureas.

Copper(II) forms with these ligands two main types of complexes: (1) Rose-red copper-bis-guanylalkoxyethylureas formed at or above pH 7. These complexes are more soluble in water and ethanol than the corresponding complexes of guanylmethylurea and guanylethylurea. The molar conductance values ($186-216 \text{ ohms}^{-1}$) indicate their bi-univalent nature. These show an absorption maximum in the range $530-540 \text{ m}\mu$ and give a paramagnetic moment value of $1.67-1.72 \text{ B.M.}$, indicative of a square planar structure with $3d^9 4s^0 4p^2$ hybrid bonds. (2) Blue-coloured copper-mono-guanylalkoxyethylureas formed from the bis-compounds at pH 3-4. These absorb at $650-660 \text{ m}\mu$ and are also paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} 1.74-1.78 \text{ B.M.}$).

Nickel(II) gives rise to the yellow to orange-yellow bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea complexes. Of these, nickel bis-guanylethoxyethylurea and nickel-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea salts change to the complex nickel base on heating with water. These are diamagnetic and show an absorption maximum at $450 \text{ m}\mu$. These two properties provide strong support to the square planar structure of the complexes with $3d^8 4s^0 4p^2$ bonding.

Palladium (II) also produces pale cream-coloured bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea complexes. These are also diamagnetic, suggesting a square planar arrangement around palladium.

In part I of this series it has been reported that an alcohol and dicyandiamide react in the presence of copper acetate, leading to the formation of the copper complex of the corresponding guanylalkylurea. With ethanol, the following reactions occur:

A large number of monohydric alcohols, namely, methyl, ethyl, propylⁱ, butyl^a, butylⁱ, amylⁱ, hexyl^a, cyclohexyl, and benzyl, were found to respond to this reaction. A comprehensive study of the copper (II), nickel (II), palladium (II), and cobalt (III) complexes of these ligands has also been recorded in this series (Dutta and Rây, this *Journal*, 1959, **36**, 499, 567, 576; Dutta, *ibid.*, 1960, **37**, 499; Dutta *et al.*, 1960, **37**, 565, 573, 789).

Ethylene glycol was expected to combine with two molecules of dicyandiamide. Only one alcoholic OH group, however, participated in the reaction, producing in presence of a copper salt the copper complex of guanylhydroxyethylurea (I). This conclusion was made on the basis of the analytical values of the copper complex.

(I)

Furthermore, the copper complexes, derived from the reaction of monohydric alcohols with dicyandiamide, were stable enough to be formed by prolonged heating under reflux on a boiling water bath. This, however, was not the case with ethylene glycol. The complex copper acetate had to be obtained by heating copper acetate, dicyandiamide, and ethylene glycol at 60° and that, too, for a short period. Evidently the complexes of guanylhydroxyethylurea were less stable.

In this paper we describe the results of our studies with three substituted ethylene glycols—one of the two alcoholic -OH groups of ethylene glycol being substituted by alkoxy groups so that these behave as monohydric alcohols. These are ethylene glycol monoalkyl ethers, *i. e.*, the alkoxyethanols, commercially known as cellosolves (methyl, ethyl and butyl cellosolves).

(II)

(III)

[R = CH₃, C₂H₅ or C₄H₁₀]

The present paper deals with the isolation of these guanylalkoxyethylurea reagents and the preparation and properties of the copper(II), nickel (II), and palladium(II) complexes of these ligands.

When copper acetate, dicyandiamide, and the alkoxyethanols (II) are heated on the water bath, after two to three hours, a deep violet solution forms, which is filtered and is allowed to crystallise. The complex copper-bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea acetate is converted to the sulphate, then decomposed by H₂S and the reagents, guanylalkoxyethylureas (III), are isolated as their sulphate salts. These are very soluble in water and give rise to the usual reactions: with copper, rose red precipitate; with nickel, yellow precipitate; with palladium, pale cream-coloured precipitate in alkaline medium.

The copper (II) complexes described in this paper are of the following different types:

(1). Copper-bis-guanylalkoxyethylureas, $[\text{Cu}(\text{Gau})_2]$, where GauH is a molecule of guanylalkoxyethylurea. These are obtained as rose-red crystalline precipitates by the addition of alkali to an aqueous solution of the complex copper-bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea acetate or chloride. The substances can be readily purified by crystallization from hot ethanol. These do not suffer any loss on reasonable heating, thus confirming the anhydro-base formula and indicating that the ligands have one acidic-NH group and another NH_2 -group to function as a donor—thus behaving as bidentate units. On heating with ammonium salts these liberate ammonia with the formation of the corresponding copper-bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea salts. These are, unlike the complex of parent guanylurea, stable to hot water or ethanol.

(2). Copper-bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea salts, $[\text{Cu}(\text{GauH}^-)_2]\text{X}_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $\text{X} = \text{CH}_3\text{COO}$, $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$, Cl, I, NO_3 , NO_2 , ClO_4 , $\frac{1}{2}\text{S}_2\text{O}_6$, $\frac{1}{2}\text{CrO}_4$. These are all rose-red to red-violet in colour excepting the chromate, which is yellow. The molar conductance values (186.6, 216.8, 208.4 ohms^{-1}) of the complex copper chloride salts of these guanylureas in water are in fair agreement with that for bi-univalent electrolytes. The solubility of these complexes calls for comment.

In the series of the guanylalkylureas, the solubility of the complex copper chloride, acetate, or the thiocyanate in water definitely falls off with increase in the chain length of the substituent. On the other hand, solubility in ethanol increases. Thus the complex copper chloride of guanylmethylurea and of guanylethylurea are soluble in water but insoluble in alcohol; copper-guanylpropylurea chloride is soluble in water and also in ethanol, whereas those of guanylbutylurea, guanylamylurea, guanylhethylurea, and guanylcyclohexylurea are insoluble in water but readily soluble in ethanol. In fact, the complex copper-guanylmethylurea chloride and guanylethylurea chloride are only moderately soluble in water and can be easily salted out by 0.2M-KCl (cf. Dutta, this *Journal*, 1960, 37, 501). The copper complexes of guanylmethoxyethylurea and of guanylethoxyethylurea are, in particular, highly soluble in water (also in ethanol)—much more so than those of guanylmethylurea or guanylethylurea. Thus crystals separate only when the solutions are highly concentrated. Even the usually insoluble salts, e.g., nitrate, bromide, iodide, perchlorate, etc., are comparatively soluble in water and even more so in ethanol. The solubility of the guanylbutoxyethylurea complexes, however, is lower than the other two. Unfortunately, we cannot comment on the solubility of the complexes of guanylpropoxyethylurea as we had no propoxyethanol at our disposal. In this context, we may mention that the copper complexes of alkoxyalkylbiguanides were found to be much more soluble than those of the alkylbiguanides (Sengupta and Rây, this *Journal*, 1959, 36, 373). The strength of the ligand field around copper(II) is generally reflected in the isolation of salts, such as, the iodide, thiocyanate, and the thiosulphate. In the series of the guanylalkylureas, the iodide and/or the thiocyanate salts have been described in most cases (cf. Part II, *loc. cit.*). In the present series, only the complex copper iodide of guanylmethoxyethylurea has been obtained in a pure state. With the other two ligands, addition of KI to the aqueous solution of the complex copper acetates liberates much iodine and an oily mass is left, indicating partial reduction of copper (II) to copper (I).

The chloride salts show in ethanol medium a rose-coloured hue with an absorption maximum at 530-540 $\text{m}\mu$ (ϵ 39-41). Ethanol was chosen as the solvent so that changes of hydrolysis would be the least.

The complexes have μ_{eff} values in the range of 1.67-1.72 B.M. (cf. Table III). According to Rây and Sen (this *Journal*, 1948, 25, 475), the somewhat lower values of the mag-

netic moments indicate these complexes to be of the square planar type with $3d_{xy}$ bonds.

(3). Copper monoguanylalkoxyethylurea chloride are blue in colour and are formed from the rose-red bis-complexes by treatment with dilute HCl (pH 3-4). At a pH 6-7 these complexes change to the rose-red bis-complexes.

In Part II of this series (*loc. cit.*) the mono-complexes of guanylmethylurea and of guanylethylurea only were described. These complexes exhibit an absorption maximum at 650-660 m μ and are also paramagnetic (μ_{eff} 1.74-1.78 B.M. Table III). The magnetic moments of copper-mono-guanylmethylurea chloride and copper mono-guanylethylurea chloride are also recorded for the sake of comparison. The values are in agreement with those (μ_{eff} 1.75-1.81 B.M.) reported by Ráy and Das Sarma for some copper monobiguanide complexes (this *Journal*, 1951, **28**, 347).

TABLE I

Conductance measurements in aqueous solution.

I. Copper bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea chloride.						
Dilution (in litres)	..	64	128	256	512	1024
Λ_v	..	72	81.5	87.3	86.4	99.8
Λ_∞	..	84.5	91.5	94.8	91.7	104.1
Λ_∞ (mean)		=93.3				
Mol. conduc.		=186.6				
II. Copper bis-guanylethoxyethylurea chloride.						
Dilution (in litres)	..	64	128	256	512	1024
Λ_v		77.9	91.1	100.7	110.3	117.0
Λ_∞		91.4	102.2	109.3	117.0	122.0
Λ_∞ (mean)		=108.4				
Mol. conduc.		=216.8				
III. Copper bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea chloride.						
Dilution (in litres)	..	64	128	256	512	1024
Λ_v		76.8	86.3	95.9	105.5	113.2
Λ_∞		90.1	95.8	104.2	112.0	118.0
Λ_∞ (mean)		=104.2				
Mol. conduc.		=208.4				
IV. Nickel bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea chloride.						
Dilution (in litres)		64	128	256	512	1024
Λ_v		80.3	93.5	101.7	110.3	115.1
Λ_∞		94.2	104.9	110.4	117.0	120.0
Λ_∞ (mean)		=109.3				
Mol. conduc.		=218.6				

The nickel (II) complexes are of two types: (1) $[(\text{Ni}(\text{Gau})_2)]$. These yellow-coloured compounds have the composition of anhydro-bases, insoluble in water but readily soluble in ethanol from which medium purification is effected. The complex nickel bases of guanylmethoxyethylurea and of guanylethoxyethylurea liberate ammonia on warming with an aqueous solution of ammonium salts and produce the corresponding salt of the $[\text{Ni}(\text{GauH}_2)]^{2+}$ ion. But similar treatment decomposes the complex nickel base of guanylbutoxyethylurea. This suggests weaker basic nature as also lower stability of the complex. (2) $[(\text{Ni}(\text{GauH})_2)] \cdot X_{2 \cdot n} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, where $X = \text{Cl}, \frac{1}{2} \text{SO}_4, \text{NO}_3, \text{NO}_2, \frac{1}{2} \text{S}_2\text{O}_6$, etc. These are all orange-yellow in colour. The chloride salt is obtained by treating the complex nickel base of guanylmethoxyethylurea and guanylethoxyethylurea with dilute HCl in aqueous solution and then precipitating with acetone. From this salt, other salts have been obtained by metathesis with appropriate alkali metal salts in aqueous-alcoholic medium. The solubility of these nickel complexes, however, is much less than the corresponding copper complexes. The complex nickel bases of guanylmethoxyethylurea and guanylethoxyethylurea could be treated with dilute acids in aqueous medium to furnish salts of the type $[(\text{Ni}(\text{GauH})_2)^{2+}]$, whereas the complex nickel base of guanylbutoxyethylurea decomposed under similar treatment in aqueous medium. This base could, however, be neutralised with ethanolic dilute HCl in ethanol medium to produce the chloride salt. The chloride salt, however, decomposes to the base readily on treatment with hot water. The change occurs possibly through the formation of the hydrated base:

The aqueous solution of the complex nickel-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea chloride turns turbid on standing due to a similar change to the insoluble complex nickel base. The corresponding solution of the nickel-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea is more stable. This points towards a decrease in the stability from guanylmethoxyethylurea to the guanylbutoxyethylurea through guanylethoxyethylurea. The corresponding copper complexes are far too stable to undergo such a change to the complex base. This is an indication of the higher stability of the copper complexes. In this context it may be mentioned that the complex nickel base of the parent compound, guanylurea, changes readily into the simple nickel salts in neutral or a slightly acid solution so that no salt of the complex nickel-guanylurea base could be prepared (Rây and Bandapadhyay, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 865). A study of the dissociation constant of these guanylalkoxyethylureas and of the stability of the copper and nickel complexes are therefore expected to throw more light into such behaviour of these complexes. We propose to undertake such a study in future.

The aqueous solution of the complex nickel-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea is stable enough to allow measurements of the conductance at various dilutions. The Λ_∞ values calculated from the Λ_v values by Walden's formula (cf. Parts II-VI, *loc. cit.*) are in very close agreement with those of a bi-univalent electrolyte (cf. Table I). Conductance values of the other two nickel complexes had to be measured in methanol. The Λ_v values are, however, somewhat lower than the limiting value (105 ohms⁻¹) of such electrolytes in methanol. These values, when plotted against concentration, gives a straight line, which on extrapolation to zero concentration provides values of ca. 95 ohms⁻¹.

TABLE II

Conductance measurements in methanol solution.

Dilution.	Equivalent conductance (Λ_v)	
	Nickel-bis-guanylalkoxyethylurea chloride Ethoxy.	Butoxy.
256 litres	69.6	69.6
512	77.8	77.5
1024	80.6	82.5

The complex nickel bases as well as their salts have been found to be diamagnetic (Table III). In this connection some recent works on the nickel(II) complexes may be mentioned. It has been shown from ligand-field considerations that planar, tetraco-ordinate complexes of Ni (II) may be either paramagnetic or diamagnetic, depending on the strength of the ligand field. Bis-acetylacetonickel (II) has been cited as a prominent example of a planar paramagnetic material (Liehr and Ballhausen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **81**, 528). This substance is, however, known to form a dihydrate readily, suggesting a strong tendency for the nickel(II) to become octahedrally surrounded. Molecular weight measurements in dichloromethane, again, indicate substantial polymerization. Besides, bis-(2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-3,5-heptanediono)-nickel (II) is red, anhydrous, and diamagnetic. Again, bis-(2,2-dimethyl-3,5-heptanediono)-nickel (II) is green, paramagnetic, but interesting is the observation that the toluene solution of the compound is green at 0° and red at 50°. The nickel complex of 3-phenyl-2,4-pentanedione behaves similarly (Fackler and Cotton, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 5005).

Paramagnetism in these complexes may well be attributed to intermolecular association giving octahedral $4s4p^3d^2$ bondings. The nickel complexes, described in this paper, give convincing diamagnetic values. These diamagnetic values together with strong absorption bands at 450 m μ (ϵ 4.3-4.6) lend strong support for their square planar structure with $3d4s4p^3$ hybrid bonds. An absorption band near 400 m μ and/or diamagnetism in tetraco-ordinated nickel (II) complexes has been regarded as diagnostic of a square planar arrangement (Nyholm, *Chem. Rev.*, 1953, **53**, 263). Thus, the guanylalkoxyethylureas set strong enough a ligand field around nickel (II).

Palladium (II) reacts with these ligands in alkaline medium to form cream-coloured palladium-bis-guanylalkoxyethylureas. These also correspond to the composition of anhydro-bases (cf. Part V) and can be neutralised with dilute acids to form the corresponding salts. These, too, are diamagnetic (Table III) and have a square planar structure with $4sp^2$ bonds.

TABLE III

Magnetic susceptibilities measurements.

Substance.	$\chi_g \times 10^6$.	$\chi_m \times 10^6$.	Dia. $\times 10^6$ (corr.)	$\chi_A \times 10^6$.	μ_{eff} (B.M.).
Copper-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea sulphate [Cu(C ₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂) ₂] SO ₄ ·H ₂ O	1.956	973.2	191	1164	1.67
Copper-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea sulphate [Cu(C ₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂) ₂] SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	1.856	1009	228	1237	1.72
Copper-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea sulphate [Cu(C ₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂) ₂] SO ₄ ·2.5H ₂ O	1.49	907.2	281.7	1188.7	1.68
Copper-mono-guanylmethoxyethylurea chloride [Cu(C ₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂) Cl ₂]	3.884	1143	121	1264	1.74
Copper-mono-guanylethoxyethylurea chloride [Cu(C ₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂) Cl ₂] H ₂ O	3.62	1182	145.9	1327.9	1.78
Copper-mono-guanylbutoxyethylurea chloride [Cu(C ₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂) Cl ₂]	3.463	1165	156.6	1321.6	1.78
Copper-mono-guanylmethylurea chloride [Cu(C ₃ H ₈ N ₄ O) Cl ₂]	4.483	1123	99	1222	1.71
Copper-mono-guanylethylurea chloride [Cu(C ₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ O) Cl ₂]	4.82	1275	110.9	1385.9	1.82
Nickel-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea [Ni(C ₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	-0.41	-155.4	-	-	Diamagnetic
Nickel-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea [Ni(C ₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	-0.47	-191.2	-	-	"
Nickel-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea [Ni(C ₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	-0.35	-162.0	-	-	"
Nickel-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea sulphate [Ni(C ₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂) ₂] SO ₄ ·1.5H ₂ O	-0.31	-155.4	-	-	"
Palladium-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea [Pd(C ₅ H ₁₂ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	-0.20	-85.4	-	-	"
Palladium-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea [Pd(C ₆ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	-0.25	-114.0	-	-	"
Palladium-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea [Pd(C ₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ O ₂) ₂]	-0.56	-286.0	-	-	"

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper Complexes

Copper-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea Acetate.—Copper acetate (25 g.), dicyandiamide (25 g.), and methyl cellosolve (10 c.c.) were refluxed on the water bath for 3-4 hours. The dark rose-red solution along with some crystals was transferred to a beaker and allowed to stand overnight. Next day the crystals were filtered, dissolved in hot water or ethanol, filtered, and allowed to crystallize in vacuum. This is highly soluble in water and ethanol but insoluble in acetone.

Base.—An aqueous solution of the complex copper acetate was treated with NaOH solution when the crude base separated. This was purified by recrystallization from hot ethanol. This is insoluble in water but soluble in ethanol and acetone. This reacts alkaline to litmus and liberates ammonia on heating with ammonium salts.

Chloride.—The complex copper acetate (1 g. in 10 c.c. water) was treated with a large amount of KCl and the solution allowed to stand in the frigidaire for a day or two when rose-red crystals separated. These were filtered, dissolved in hot ethanol, filtered from the contaminated KCl, and allowed to crystallize in vacuum. This is readily soluble in water and ethanol but insoluble in acetone.

The other salts were obtained by metathesis between the complex copper acetate and the appropriate alkali metal salt in aqueous medium and whenever possible purified by recrystallization from water or ethanol. The nitrate, bromide, iodide, and the perchlorate have appreciable solubility in warm water or ethanol.

Copper-mono-guanylmethoxyethylurea Chloride.—Copper bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea chloride was dissolved in little water and the solution treated with dilute HCl till the colour changed from red violet to intense blue (pH 3-4). This was then dried in vacuum. The blue and rose-coloured residue was treated repeatedly with cold methanol containing a drop or two of dilute HCl, when a clear blue crystalline powder was left. The was filtered, washed with acidic (HCl) methanol, and dried in air. The washings of this preparation on standing provided another crop of light blue crystals.

Copper-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea Chloride.—The complex copper-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea base (obtained from the acetate by the action of NaOH) was neutralised with dilute HCl, filtered, and the violet-red solution allowed to crystallize in *vacuo* over H_2SO_4 .

Other complexes of copper were obtained by following similar procedures as described above. In Tables IV, V and VI are recorded the analytical results of the copper (II) complexes.

TABLE IV

Complex compounds of copper with guanylmethoxyethylurea.

	Found.	Calc.
1. Copper-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea [Cu (x) ₂]	Cu : 16.81% N : 30.06	16.64% 29.35
2. Acetate [Cu (xH) ₂] (CH ₃ COO) ₂	Cu : 12.90	12.66
3. Sulphate [Cu(xH) ₂]SO ₄ ·H ₂ O	Cu : 12.71 N : 21.95 SO ₄ : 18.95 *H ₂ O : 3.20	12.76 22.51 19.90 3.61

TABLE IV (contd.)

	Found.	Calc.
4. Chloride [Cu(xH) ₂] Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	Cu : 13.25 N : 24.16 Cl : 15.00	13.44 23.70 15.03
5. Bromide [Cu(xH) ₂] Br ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Cu : 11.10 Br : 27.30 H ₂ O: 7.00	10.96 27.59 6.21
6. Iodide [Cu(xH) ₂] I ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O*	Cu : 9.24 I : 36.95 H ₂ O: 6.20	9.31% 37.20 6.59
7. Nitrate [Cu(xH) ₂] (NO ₃) ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O	Cu : 11.61	11.50
8. Perchlorate [Cu(xH) ₂] (ClO ₄) ₂ ·0.5H ₂ O	Cu : 11.00 N ₂ : 19.22	10.73 18.93
9. Nitrite [Cu(xH) ₂] (NO ₂) ₂ ·1.5H ₂ O	Cu : 12.66	12.64
10. Dithionate [Cu(xH) ₂] S ₂ O ₆ ·1.5H ₂ O	Cu : 10.95 H ₂ O: 4.40	11.13 4.73
11. Copper-mono-guanylmethoxy- ethylurea chloride [Cu(xH) Cl ₂]	Cu : 21.40 N : 19.07 Cl : 23.80	21.57 19.02 24.12

*H₂O by loss at 110°.

xH stands for a molecule of guanylmethoxyethylurea, C₅H₁₂N₄O₂.

TABLE V

Complex compounds of copper with guanylethoxyethylurea.

	Found.	Calc.
1. Copper-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea [Cu(x) ₂]	Cu : 15.41% N : 27.37	15.51% 27.35
2. Acetate [Cu(xH) ₂] (CH ₃ COO) ₂	Cu : 11.37 H ₂ O: 6.50	11.23 6.36
3. Sulphate [Cu(xH) ₂] SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Cu : 11.68 N : 20.10 SO ₄ : 17.86 H ₂ O: 6.26	11.68 20.60 17.66 6.62
4. Chloride [Cu(xH) ₂] Cl ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Cu : 11.50 N : 20.66 Cl : 13.21 H ₂ O: 9.30	11.83 20.87 13.23 10.07
5. Nitrate [Cu(xH) ₂] (NO ₃) ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Cu : 10.80 H ₂ O: 10.00	10.77 9.16
6. Dithionate [Cu(xH) ₂] S ₂ O ₆ ·2.5H ₂ O	Cu : 10.27 H ₂ O: 6.90	10.30 7.30
7. Copper-mono-guanylethoxyethylurea chloride [Cu(xH)Cl ₂]H ₂ O	Cu : 19.56 N : 17.30 Cl : 21.50	19.45 17.15 21.74

xH stands for a molecule of guanylethoxyethylurea C₆H₁₄N₄O₂.

TABLE VI

Complex compounds of copper with guanylbutoxyethylurea.

	Found.	Calc.
1. Copper-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea [Cu(x) ₂]	Cu : 13.60% N : 23.72	13.64% 24.05
2. Acetate [Cu(xH) ₂] (CH ₃ COO) ₂ .2H ₂ O	Cu : 10.40 H ₂ O: 6.00	10.22 5.79
3. Sulphate [Cu(xH) ₂] SO ₄ .2.5H ₂ O	Cu : 10.55 SO ₄ : 15.50 H ₂ O: 7.00	10.44 15.77 7.99
4. Chloride [Cu(xH) ₂] Cl ₂ .1.5H ₂ O	Cu : 11.14 N : 20.30 Cl : 12.41	11.23 19.81 12.56
5. Nitrate [Cu (xH) ₂] (NO ₃) ₂ .3H ₂ O	Cu : 9.81 H ₂ O : 9.00	9.84 8.36
6. Copper-mono-guanylbutoxyethylurea chloride [Cu(xH)Cl ₂]	Cu : 18.54 N : 16.62 Cl : 21.50	18.87 16.64 21.10

xH stands for a molecule of guanylbutoxyethylurea, C₈H₁₈N₄O₂.

Nickel Complexes

Nickel-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea Base.—Copper-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea sulphate was suspended in water, treated with H₂S, filtered, and the filtrate treated with air till free of H₂S. Nickelacetate was then added and the solution made strongly alkaline. The precipitated yellow complex nickel base was filtered, washed with water, and purified from hot ethanol.

Chloride.—The complex nickel base was triturated with HCl (dil.) to a faintly acid reaction when a deep orange solution formed. This solution was treated with acetone and allowed to stand overnight in the cold. The dark orange crystals were filtered, washed with acetone, and dried in air. This is readily soluble in water and ethanol.

The other salts were obtained as for the complex copper salts. Nickel complexes of guanylethoxyethylurea were also obtained by the above procedures.

Nickel-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea Chloride.—The complex nickel base was dissolved in ethanol, neutralised with HCl, filtered, and allowed to concentrate in vacuum. Orange-yellow crystals together with some oil separated. This was then allowed to stand in the frigidaire for several hours when the oil changed to crystals. The crystals were filtered, washed with cold aqueous ethanol, and dried over CaCl₂. This is readily soluble in ethanol but insoluble in water. On heating with water, the orange-yellow chloride changes to the yellow-coloured base.

The complex sulphate and the nitrate were obtained by neutralising the ethanol solution of the complex base with dilute H₂SO₄ or dilute HNO₃. The analytical results of the nickel complexes are given in Tables VII-IX.

TABLE VII

Complex compounds of nickel with guanylmethoxyethylurea.

	Found.	Calc.
1. Nickel-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea [Ni(x) ₂]	Ni : 15.53% N : 29.25	15.58% 29.73
2. Sulphate [Ni(xH) ₂]SO ₄ ·1.5H ₂ O	Ni : 11.77 N : 21.90 SO ₄ : 18.86	11.70 22.33 19.14
3. Chloride [Ni(xH) ₂]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	Ni : 11.82 N : 22.55 Cl : 14.95	12.09 23.06 14.62
4. Iodide [Ni(xH) ₂]I ₂ ·2.5H ₂ O	Ni : 8.97 I : 38.73 H ₂ O : 4.82	8.90 38.49 4.09
5. Nitrate [Ni(xH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	Ni : 10.12 H ₂ O : 12.20	10.21 12.53
6. Dithionate [Ni(xH) ₂]S ₂ O ₆ ·3H ₂ O	Ni : 9.81 H ₂ O : 9.60	9.90 9.11

TABLE VIII

Complex compounds of nickel with guanylethoxyethylurea.

	Found.	Calc.
1. Nickel-bis-guanylethoxyethylurea [Ni(x) ₂]	Ni : 14.20% N : 27.00	14.50% 27.67
2. Sulphate [Ni(xH) ₂]SO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	Ni : 11.01 N : 20.34 SO ₄ : 18.10	10.90 20.87 17.82
3. Chloride [Ni(xH) ₂]Cl ₂ ·3H ₂ O	Ni : 10.80 Cl : 13.43 H ₂ O : 9.42	11.04 13.35 10.10
4. Nitrate [Ni(xH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂ ·3.5H ₂ O	Ni : 9.87 H ₂ O : 11.01	9.88 10.61
5. Nitrite [Ni(xH) ₂](NO ₂) ₂ ·0.5H ₂ O	Ni : 11.74 N : 1.90	11.56 1.77
6. Dithionate [Ni(xH) ₂]S ₂ O ₆ ·2H ₂ O	Ni : 9.88 H ₂ O : 6.20	9.74 5.97

TABLE IX

Complex compounds of nickel with guanylbutoxyethylurea.

	Found.	Calc.
1. Nickel-bis-guanylbutoxyethylurea [Ni(x) ₂]	Ni : 12.87% N : 24.33	12.74% 24.30
2. Sulphate [Ni(xH) ₂]SO ₄	Ni : 10.75 N : 20.60 SO ₄ : 17.68	10.51 20.05 17.19
3. Chloride [Ni(xH) ₂]Cl ₂ ·H ₂ O	Ni : 10.38 N : 20.70 Cl : 13.75	10.64 20.30 12.87
4. Nitrate [Ni(xH) ₂](NO ₃) ₂	Ni : 10.34	10.00

Palladium Complexes

Sodium chloropalladite was added to the freshly prepared solution of the reagents (obtained from the complex Cu salts by H_2S , as described above under nickel) and the solution made strongly alkaline with $NaOH$. The precipitated complex palladium base was further purified for hot ethanol.

{Found: Pd, 25.62; N, 25.85. $[Pd(C_5H_{11}N_4O_2)_2]$ requires Pd, 25.13; N, 26.37%}.

{Found: Pd, 24.00; N, 24.70. $[Pd(C_6H_{13}N_4O_2)_2]$ requires Pd, 23.57; N, 14.74%}.

{Found: Pd, 20.83; N, 21.65. $[Pd(C_8H_{17}N_4O_2)_2]$ requires Pd, 20.97; N, 22.02%}.

Reagents

Guanylmethoxyethylurea Sulphate.—Complex copper-bis-guanylmethoxyethylurea sulphate (10 g.) was finely powdered, suspended in water (20 c.c.), treated with H_2S , filtered, and the filtrate treated with air till free of H_2S . The solution was then filtered, cooled in ice, and treated with acetone when an oil separated, which on scratching changed into colorless crystals.

The other two reagents also separated initially as oil, but on repeated scratching with fresh acetone, these changed into crystalline form. Because of the very high solubility of the reagents in water, no further purification was attempted.

{Found : N, 26.80; SO_4 , 22.79. $(C_5H_{12}N_4O_2)_2 \cdot H_2SO_4$ requires N, 26.79; SO_4 , 22.96%}.

{Found : N, 22.70; SO_4 , 22.02. $(C_6H_{14}N_4O_2)_2 \cdot H_2SO_4 \cdot H_2O$ requires N, 24.14; SO_4 , 20.69%}.

{Found : N, 22.45; SO_4 , 19.53. $(C_8H_{16}N_4O_2)_2 \cdot H_2SO_4$ requires N, 22.31; SO_4 , 19.13%}.

Magnetic Measurements

The magnetic moments were obtained by the Gouy method using a semi-micro Mettler balance for measuring the difference in weight and a field strength of 9.26 gauss. Pascal's constants were used in calculating the corrections for the diamagnetism of the ligands (Selwood, "Magnetochemistry").

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